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ORGANIZATION OF TEACHING METHODS AND REQUIREMENTS FOR LESSONS

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Annotation: *Education has played a significant role in the development of human society from its early stages. Throughout the history of the school's progress, various forms of organizing education have emerged. The forms of organizing education have been shaped in accordance with the specific social structure and the benefits of that structure. In a continuously evolving society, education in its complete form, namely lessons, has been improving for several years, and the requirements placed on it have become more complex and modernized.*

Keywords: *education and its organizational forms, classroom lesson system, types of lessons, requirements for lessons, group activities, lectures, practical and laboratory exercises, seminars, excursions, practice, coursework, self-learning.*

Annotatsiya: *Ta'lim insoniyat jamiyati rivojlanishining dastlabki paytlaridayoq katta rol o'ynagan. Maktabning tarixan taraqqiy etish davrida ta'limni tashkil qilish shakllari turlicha bo'lgan. Ta'limni tashkil etish shakllari ma'lum ijtimoiy tuzum va shu tuzumning manfaatlariga mos holda shakllangan. Uzluksiz rivojlangan jamiyatda ta'limning mukammal jamoa shakli ya'ni dars necha yillardan beri takomillashib, unga qo'yilgan talablar murakkablashib va zamonaviylashib bormoqda.*

Tayanch iboralar: *ta'lim va uning tashkiliy shakllari, sinf-dars tizimi, dars turlari, darsga qo'yilgan talablar, guruhli mashg'ulotlar, ma'ruza, amaliy va laboratoriya mashg'uloti, seminar, ekskursiya, amaliyot, kurs ishi, mustaqil ta'lim;*

Introduction: The educational process in Uzbekistan began before the period of independence and has been conducted in traditional and non-traditional, online and offline teaching methods until the present day. The education system has its own stages and history. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education," it is stated that "Higher education ensures the training of highly qualified specialists." In addition, higher education also teaches students scientific research work. Our leader

has emphasized that "No one can deny the great importance of higher education institutions, especially in relation to the generation that is coming. Educating and raising the youth, contributing to the formation of highly qualified specialists in an independent country is our sacred duty." From this point of view, providing education in higher education institutions in the current era has special significance. Currently, higher education consists of two stages: bachelor's and master's. In order to implement these stages, various organizational forms of teaching are used in the training of highly qualified specialists with clear goals and rich knowledge. The organizational forms of teaching and knowledge transfer in higher education institutions are based on the Law "On Education" and the "National Program for Personnel Training." At the end of the 16th century and the beginning of the 17th century, the great Czech pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius (1592-1670) pioneered the creation of the classroom lesson system in the history of education [L.1].

Teaching methods and approaches. Despite facing serious resistance to Jan Amos Comenius's ideas on organizing education, Western countries quickly embraced them and recognized the classroom lesson system as a systematic form of education. However, the system of classroom lessons was not implemented in Eastern countries, including the ancient Muslim states in Central Asia. The oral teaching method began to be practiced in the Latin language in the 18th century in line with societal development. Presentations started to be read in the Russian language in the mid-18th century. One of its prominent representatives was M.V. Lomonosov. Until 1917, the educational system (format) specific to the middle schools continued. In these schools, children aged 6 to 15-16 were engaged in activities in a single room at the same time. Consequently, the levels of knowledge and learning outcomes of children varied. Up until the present day, the organizational form of group activities, referred to as the classroom lesson system, has significantly expanded, strengthened, and evolved over time, as well as the organizational forms and teaching methods of education. A class consists of a group of students who are of the same age and have similar levels of knowledge.

A lesson refers to the educational activity conducted by a teacher with a specific group of students. A lesson is the fundamental organizational form of teaching. It is the central part of the teaching activities [L.2].

In our schools, the classroom lesson system is implemented in the following organizational forms:

Each class consists of a permanent group of children of the same age and level of knowledge.

The lesson activity is mainly structured for 45 minutes and is conducted according to a strict schedule.

Lessons are conducted in both group and individual formats, under the guidance of the teacher. The lesson is delivered using various methods depending on the content of the material, and as part of the education system, it provides completed knowledge and creates a foundation for mastering subsequent subjects.

Currently, new forms of organizing school education are being developed in accordance with the demands and needs of the people's education in our independent republic. Nowadays, there are two types of organizational forms of education in our schools: classroom lesson-based activities and practical and experiential work.

Classroom lesson-based activities involve the systematic presentation of the teacher's daily teaching material, the utilization of different methods, the thorough consideration of students' knowledge, skills, and abilities, and the promotion of independent work among students.

Practical and experiential work is conducted outside the classroom, in educational workshops, and through field trips, aimed at providing practical training and experiences beyond the classroom environment. [L.2;,3;,5].

Objectives and subjects of research.

Organizing activities in the form of classroom lessons is aimed at improving the quality of education and upbringing provided to students, considering the new tasks and requirements that exist in the field of education. The success of each lesson largely depends on the proper organization of activities. The initial period of a lesson in our schools is referred to as the organizational minutes of the lesson. However, it is necessary not to limit the lesson to a certain stage or structure. It is crucial to carefully observe the preparedness of the class during the organizational minutes. Experienced and skilled teachers take advantage of the opportunity, immediately capturing the attention of the students and starting the work. At the same time, the teacher has two tasks in front of them - to capture the attention of the entire class and ensure that all students actively engage in the activity.

The lesson starts with vividly and clearly explaining the intended goal of the lesson. If the lesson is aimed at presenting new material, the topic of the lesson is announced. Once the planned material in the lesson plan is covered, it is necessary for it to be concluded and the main points to be summarized. Additionally, the teacher's use of effective pedagogical technologies, employing various teaching methods, and creating more challenging situations for the students to encounter, enhances the quality of the lesson by presenting new material to them. [L.5;,6;,7].

The main purpose of organizing and conducting a lesson is to ensure the effectiveness of the learning process. For this purpose:

a) It is important for teachers to present the intended goal derived from the taught subject, allowing students to actively comprehend the material. In other words, the

teacher should provide opportunities for students to express independent thoughts and encourage critical thinking;

b) Within the allocated time, the teacher should present the materials in an organized and clear manner, ensuring that students also independently work on the topic. While explaining the subject matter, the teacher should pose thought-provoking questions that challenge the students to think and explore, thus enabling them to internalize the material.

c) During the process of presenting knowledge, it is necessary to involve students in active learning (oral, written exercises, laboratory experiments, independent creative work). This, in turn, helps students apply the knowledge they have acquired and provides ample opportunity for accurate evaluation.

d) It is also important to demonstrate the relevance of the taught materials to other related subjects during the lesson.

Components of teaching and upbringing activities in a lesson: goal, content, tools, methods, organization, management, and all its didactic elements are considered integrated. Therefore, in order to properly address the issues of teaching, the teacher needs to understand the main components of the educational process, their interdependence, and their impact on each other. In general, both reproductive and creative tasks can be given to students in the classroom. [L.3;5;6].

Purpose and objectives of research:

A lesson is a form of organizing the activities of teachers and students, aimed at teaching, nurturing, and developing children. The organization of teaching is not a fixed form. Educational practice and pedagogical thought constantly seek ways to improve it. Many experiments are being carried out in this field.

A lesson should meet the following general didactic requirements, taking into account various thoughts and opinions:

1. Each lesson should have a specific goal and a well-structured plan.
2. Each lesson should be based on a strong theoretical and practical basis.
3. Each lesson should be linked to life and practice, using various methods, approaches, and tools effectively.
4. Each hour and minute allocated for the lesson should be used wisely.
5. The unity of the teacher's and students' activity should be ensured in the lesson.
6. The lesson should create opportunities for using informative materials, technical tools, and computers.
7. Individual characteristics of each student should be taken into account during the lesson.

The most commonly used types of lessons in the education system are as follows:

- Lecture on presenting new knowledge.
- Lesson on consolidating previously learned material.
- Lesson on checking and evaluating students' knowledge, skills, and abilities.
- Recap and introductory lessons.
- Combined lessons (utilizing multiple types mentioned above).

Each type of lesson has its own structure and characteristics, which help the teacher to present the educational material correctly and effectively, consolidate it in the students' minds, monitor its assimilation, and ensure its internalization. One of the most commonly used types of lessons in our schools is the lecture on presenting new knowledge. This type of lesson is structured as follows:

- a) Presenting new knowledge.
- b) Consolidating new knowledge.
- c) Working on new knowledge.
- d) Assigning homework related to new knowledge.

So, a lesson is not just conducted with a single type of lesson, but rather it can include other elements such as reinforcing new knowledge through question-answer sessions, practicing on new knowledge through problem-solving and examples, assigning homework (which serves as another lesson element, providing explanations, showing instructions, etc.). Therefore, if the purpose of the lesson is to impart new knowledge to students, all didactic methods are applied to achieve that goal. That's why such a lesson is called a lesson of imparting new knowledge. [L.4;6;7].

The structure of a lesson explains its organization and its parts. However, the organization of a lesson type is not determined solely by its structure. It is determined by the teaching method it is associated with. In other words, the change in the organization of the lesson also leads to a change in the teaching method used. The organization of the lesson is related to the set goals, the content of the material being taught, the teaching methods and techniques used in the lesson, the level of preparedness and competence of the students, and their place in the learning process of the lesson.

The transition from the first to the second organization of the lesson and thus the change in the form and methods of the lesson are referred to as the stages of the lesson. For example, the organization of a mixed type of lesson includes:

- Asking homework questions, checking them;
- Presenting new materials;
- Reinforcing new materials;

- Assigning homework. In this case:

a) Asking homework questions can be done through conversation (question-answer), using examples and problems. This is the first part of the lesson organization, the first stage of the lesson.

b) During the presentation of new materials, the teacher can use explanations, storytelling, school presentation, conversation methods. This is the second part of the lesson organization, the second stage of the lesson.

c) During the reinforcement of new materials, the teacher can use conversation, exercises, working with books. This is the third part of the lesson organization, the third stage of the lesson.

d) During the assignment of homework, instructions are given. Conversation method can be used. This is the fourth part of the lesson organization, the fourth stage of the lesson. As seen above, all types of lessons mentioned have their own structure, and they are also divided into specific stages.

A recap and generalization lesson is usually conducted after covering a specific part or a major topic of the curriculum. In this case, the review of the covered materials is considered with the aim of revisiting and reinforcing the topics covered by using questions related to the covered topics and interrelated questions. [L.3;,4;,5].

Organization of teaching in higher educational institutions yields expected results.

The process of teaching in higher education is carried out based on a comprehensive system of organizing teaching methods and approaches. The classification of teaching methods and techniques in higher educational institutions is interconnected and related to two types of activities:

- The activities of teachers in managing and organizing the learning process;
- The learning and cognitive activities of students.

The forms of the learning process in higher education include lectures, seminars, practical exercises, laboratory work, study forums, consultations, excursions, expeditions, pedagogical activities in developing educational materials, course and diploma works, and independent learning by students [L.5;,6;,7].

A lecture is a form of knowledge delivery where the teacher (educator) explains scientific knowledge, skills, and techniques to students. The lecture is one of the traditional methods of the learning process, initially appearing as reading a book or explaining its content. The main tasks addressed in lectures on subjects include:

- Presenting a specific amount of scientific knowledge;
- Introducing students to the methodology of the subject and research;

- Demonstrating methodological connections between various types of learning activities and exercises. Lectures are differentiated based on the didactic objective (direction), thematic content, and general-conclusive presentations.

Practical exercises are the logical continuation of learning activities and represent the overall concept of independent work in a classroom. If lectures present the fundamental scientific knowledge, practical exercises deepen, expand, and detail these knowledge areas. Importantly, practical exercises serve to test students' knowledge. Practical exercises include exercises, conducting laboratory work, and carrying out various scientific experiments. The theoretical knowledge gained from lectures is directly connected and put into practice during practical exercises, where students conduct experiments. One of the forms of practical exercises is a seminar.

A **seminar** is an educational form organized with the aim of expanding and deepening the theoretical knowledge acquired by students. During a seminar, the teacher's role is elevated, meaning the teacher does not provide direct answers to the students' questions, but rather organizes discussions and guides the process. Preparing for a seminar requires students to take considerable responsibility. Specifically, students should engage in independent reading, work with necessary literature, search for additional sources related to the topic, and present their findings.

Laboratory activities - In this case, students perform independent tasks or conduct experiments. Laboratory activities shape the research skills of students, provide a practical orientation towards the subject and technology, and enable the acquisition of the general methodology of experimentation. Laboratory activities are usually conducted in a specially equipped room with the necessary apparatus and tools, such as microscopes, magnifying glasses, flasks, measuring instruments, and other equipment, in an appropriate space (the classroom).

Excursion - It is a form of education and training where things and events being studied are explored in their natural conditions (visiting a plant, factory, field, or observing nature) or in special institutions (museums, exhibitions, etc.) in an organized manner. The excursion method involves the presentation and explanation of the object being observed by the teacher or the responsible person conducting the excursion. At the end of the excursion, a concluding lesson is usually held, where materials prepared by students, such as drawings, pictures, impressions, etc., are used. The teacher summarizes observations and ideas and concludes the activity.

Practice - It is another form of education where theoretical knowledge gained by students in higher education is directly applied. During practice, future professionals are trained in real-life situations. Practice is the first step in the future professional activity of a student and helps evaluate how well they can apply the theoretical knowledge acquired during their studies, enabling them to envision their future.

Coursework - It is one of the forms of education prescribed in the curriculum of higher education. Coursework is carried out after completing the theoretical course of a particular subject. This type of education is based on reinforcing and linking theoretical knowledge with practical application during the period of knowledge acquisition. Coursework can be included in independent work assignments. Coursework is also included in the curriculum.

Dissertation - It represents the outcome of a student's academic knowledge acquired during their studies in higher education, and it serves as an initial form of scientific research. A dissertation is a form of education that is completed by a student in a particular field, usually in collaboration with a supervisor in that field, and it is one of the prescribed forms of education in the higher education curriculum. [L.6 7]

Conclusion

The organization and implementation of independent learning and teaching in a higher secondary school would be in line with the intended purpose. Independent work by students, their analysis, expanding and deepening their knowledge, has a positive effect on their cognitive abilities and leads to new aspirations. If the tasks and goals of independent learning are defined as follows, good results can be achieved:

1. The objectives of independent learning are to enhance a person's intellectual capabilities, improve their theoretical and conceptual level, and develop their professional skills and culture.
2. The main purpose of independent learning is to stimulate students' creative search, work on their own, and enhance their personal and professional qualities. To ensure the effectiveness and purposefulness of activities, a plan is developed. In general, various forms of organizing the learning process are implemented in all higher secondary schools, and a number of requirements are set for them.

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